

CoreTrustSeal Board Response to the OSTP Draft Desirable Characteristics of Repositories for Managing and Sharing Data

Responding organization: CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board (<https://www.coretrustseal.org/>)

Domain: Digital preservation

Role: Certification Body

The CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board appreciates the opportunity to provide comments to the Draft Desirable Characteristics of Repositories for Managing and Sharing Data. The CoreTrustSeal began as a World Data System–Data Seal of Approval effort under the Research Data Alliance to develop a core set of trustworthy data repository (TDR) requirements in response to stakeholder demand for a single, common, community standard and process with a low barrier to entry. The CoreTrustSeal Board and community welcomes all work to further define the desirable characteristics of repositories and seeks to engage with such processes whenever possible. The Board would also welcome feedback on the CoreTrustSeal TDR Requirements¹, which remain community driven and subject to ongoing review and approval.

We are pleased that the proposed characteristics align strongly with the content of the CoreTrustSeal TDR Requirements. In our response, we seek to identify those alignments, comment on the characteristics as provided, and clarify any cases where the specifics are out of the current scope of the CoreTrustSeal.

Overall comments

In addition to the direct responses below, there are one or two overall comments and a suggestion for an additional characteristic.

L. *Evidence of alignment*: Provides public evidence (documentation) sufficient to demonstrate alignment with the desirable characteristics.

As a part of the certification process and to avoid resource intensive site visits, the CoreTrustSeal requires that applicant self-assessed responses to the Requirements are supported by documented links to evidence on the web. This transparency of evidence helps ensure that the claims made by repositories are visible to their peers, as well as to the reviewers. The benefit here is that publicly visible evidence not only helps ensure honesty, but also makes available to the community a valuable resource of repository practice information. Some clarity on the level of expected evidence to support the desirable characteristics would be valuable to repositories and their depositors and users. The

¹ CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2019, November 20). CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Data Repositories Requirements 2020–2022 (Version v02.00-2020-2022). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3638211>.

evidence sought for the CoreTrustSeal TDR Requirements is not onerous and seeks to align closely with what a repository would need both to offer a consistent, high-quality service and to ensure service sustainability.

We note also that while B. *Long-term sustainability* implies the sustainable availability of the dataset, there is no explicit statement about the ongoing curation of the data (including ongoing access through format migration or emulation) or metadata (including updates to meet evolving metadata standards and the changing needs of data users). In addition to minimizing the risk of unintended change through integrity measures, sometimes referred to as bit-level preservation, many communities seek more active preservation of resources. These might include deposit, storage, and access functions provided through a generalist repository that retains rights to address changes to formats or general metadata (for discovery, identification, reuse, etc.). A further tier of care is provided by disciplinary or domain repositories with the expert knowledge necessary to offer specialist deposits, curation, access, and reuse services. Research data funders, creators, and users may benefit from a range of curation and preservation levels, but the level of care a dataset will receive should be transparent to all.

In addition to the above, we would like to encourage that repositories provide information about their governance and expert input (see, for example, CoreTrustSeal Requirements R1. Mission, R5. Organizational Infrastructure, R6. Expert Guidance). This can help demonstrate how repositories ensure the maintenance of documentation and evidence relevant to their mission, and how they support managed change over time. The information is also important to support cooperation and interoperability.

I. Desirable Characteristics for All Data Repositories

A. *Persistent Unique Identifiers*: Assigns datasets a citable, persistent unique identifier (PUID), such as a digital object identifier (DOI) or accession number, to support data discovery, reporting (e.g., of research progress), and research assessment (e.g., identifying the outputs of Federally funded research). The PUID points to a persistent landing page that remains accessible even if the dataset is de-accessioned or no longer available.

CoreTrustSeal Board comment: Aspects pertaining to this characteristic are addressed in CoreTrustSeal Requirement R13. Data discovery and identification.

“Accession number”: If there is a set of agreed criteria for an accession number/system that would align with the criteria for a PID, this could be mentioned here.

“Persistent landing page”: As written it is suggested that a “landing page” is mandated. Landing pages are a common choice of implementation, whether because there is some additional barrier to access the data (e.g., authentication/authorization) or to present the user with metadata about other versions of a dataset. So, in the absence of a standard landing page design, they can present an extra step or even a barrier to access (e.g., not supporting machine accessibility). This has been noted in work to develop automated tests of FAIRness. A more neutral statement might be to say that the PUID consistently resolves to an informative target even in the absence of the original dataset. This leaves room for data

stewards to link directly to a dataset when this is the desired functionality.

It may be worth pointing out explicitly that the data repository must have the capabilities for maintaining the persistent unique identifier to ensure that the PUID continues to point to the correct location of the dataset, even if this changes. This seems particularly relevant in cases where only an internal identifier such as an accession number is used.

B. Long-term sustainability: Has a long-term plan for managing data, including guaranteeing long-term integrity, authenticity, and availability of datasets; building on a stable technical infrastructure and funding plans; has contingency plans to ensure data are available and maintained during and after unforeseen events.

CoreTrustSeal Board comment: Aspects pertaining to this characteristic are addressed in CoreTrustSeal Requirements R3. Continuity of Access, R7. Data integrity and authenticity, R10. Preservation plan, and R16. Security.

This criterion appears to address different dimensions of sustainability: technology (including capabilities for both routinely maintaining bitstreams and disaster recovery) and financial/organizational measures to ensure that data remain available in the long term. In the experience of the CoreTrustSeal Board, these dimensions sometimes tend to be confused or to be regarded as interchangeable rather than complementary. Therefore drawing attention to the fact that, for example, sound technology without a long-term financial and organizational commitment is not sufficient for long-term sustainability may be helpful. It may also be useful to consider moving technological aspects to H. *Security*.

“Long-term”: We suggest specifying what is meant by “long-term”; for example, by pointing to an agreed definition such as the one from the OAIS Reference Model.

For repositories that are looking to obtain the CoreTrustSeal, we are seeking evidence that they have the ongoing ability to take preservation actions in response to changes to technology or to the needs of the user community. A sustainable repository can then provide assurance that it can repeatedly curate the data beyond the next round of change. This is an aspect not clearly addressed here. To clarify the scope of the suggested characteristic, we therefore suggest specifying what is meant by “availability of datasets”: Is it the availability of the “original” bitstream in unchanged form, or does it entail measures such as format migrations to ensure that the data remain usable despite technological change. You may want to refer to Requirement 10 “Preservation Plan” of the CoreTrustSeal TDR Requirements.

C. Metadata: Ensures datasets are accompanied by metadata sufficient to enable discovery, reuse, and citation of datasets, using a schema that is standard to the community the repository serves.

CoreTrustSeal Board comment: Aspects pertaining to this characteristic are addressed in CoreTrustSeal Requirements R11. Data quality, R13. Data discovery and identification, and R14. Data reuse.

The effective use of metadata is implied throughout the CoreTrustSeal, with references from relevant Requirements including appraisal, reuse and discovery (including citation). The adoption of metadata schemas that are supported by the user community are encouraged, but as yet there is neither a clear mechanism to define an acceptable community standard, nor a clear reference (e.g., registry) to record them as such. This may negatively affect the usefulness of this criterion.

D. *Curation & Quality Assurance*: Provides, or has a mechanism for others to provide, expert curation and quality assurance to improve the accuracy and integrity of datasets and metadata.

CoreTrustSeal Board comment: Aspects pertaining to this characteristic are addressed in CoreTrustSeal Requirements R8. Appraisal, R10. Preservation plan, and R14. Data reuse. In addition, see R0. Background information for a definition of curation levels.

We suggest taking into consideration that not all curation levels may include curating for the accuracy of dataset content. It may be helpful to differentiate between technical quality (standardization and compliance with norms) versus research quality assessment and action, which ideally should be carried out following the guidance of the community served.

The CoreTrustSeal Requirements (R11. Quality, in particular) also demand that a repository employs means for users to access information about data quality and other documents describing aspects of the data to support users.

Given the cost of curation and preservation, and the limited resources available to repositories, we strongly encourage that repositories should perform an appraisal function. Appraisal, following a set of selection criteria also conveyed to the depositors, is needed to ensure that the data is within scope of a particular repository and that the data has value to the community the repository serves. See CoreTrustSeal TDR Requirement R8. Appraisal for more on this aspect.

E. *Access*: Provides broad, equitable, and maximally open access to datasets, as appropriate, consistent with legal and ethical limits required to maintain privacy and confidentiality.

CoreTrustSeal Board comment: Aspects pertaining to this characteristic are addressed in CoreTrustSeal Requirements R2. Licenses, and R4. Confidentiality/Ethics.

The aspect of Open Access is largely beyond the remit of the CoreTrustSeal and therefore not covered in the CoreTrustSeal TDR Requirements. However, both E. and F. can be considered subsets of "Rights Management", including not only considerations of privacy and confidentiality, but also of Intellectual Property Rights (c.f., R2. Licenses and R4. Confidentiality/Ethics).

Echoing CoreTrustSeal Requirement R1. Mission/Scope, we also recommend that the repository should have a publicly accessible policy stating it provides access to open data that are only restricted for legal and ethical reasons. This ensures that users and depositors are made aware of the repository's commitment to Open Science.

While outside the scope of CoreTrustSeal, evaluation E. and F. touch on issues covered in

the “WDS Data Sharing Principles” (<https://www.icsu-wds.org/services/data-sharing-principles>). These, for example, also explicitly encourage that repositories enable international reuse of data.

F. Free & Easy to Access and Reuse: Makes datasets and their metadata accessible free of charge in a timely manner after submission and with broadest possible terms of reuse or documented as being in the public domain.

CoreTrustSeal Board comment: See response to E. above. In addition, it may be helpful to specify what is meant by “easy”.

G. Reuse: Enables tracking of data reuse (e.g., through assignment of adequate metadata and PUID).

CoreTrustSeal Board comment: Aspects pertaining to this characteristic are addressed in CoreTrustSeal Requirement R13. Data discovery and identification.

We suggest that this is renamed “Monitoring Reuse” or similar, rather than only “Reuse”. It does not address the capability of the dataset to be processed by software and understood by researchers, but instead the repository functions for monitoring impact, such as download statistics, altmetrics, or citation tracking.

To facilitate monitoring, we recommend for repositories to provide a suggested citation for the dataset that includes a persistent identifier. Users can then easily record the use of the dataset in published reports.

H. Secure: Provides documentation of meeting accepted criteria for security to prevent unauthorized access or release of data, such as the criteria described in the International Standards Organization's ISO 27001 (<https://www.iso.org/isoiec-27001-information-security.html>) or the National Institute of Standards and Technology's 800-53 controls (<https://nvd.nist.gov/800-53>).

CoreTrustSeal Board comment: Aspects pertaining to this characteristic are addressed in CoreTrustSeal Requirement R16. Security.

From the experience of the CoreTrustSeal Board, ISO standards can present quite a high bar for many repositories, which can be difficult to meet and which also may not always be necessary depending on the types of data curated. We therefore suggest replacing “such as” with “for example” to express stronger optionality.

We additionally recommend that the repository should provide documentation on how it protects its infrastructure to ensure continuity of service.

I. Privacy: Provides documentation that administrative, technical, and physical safeguards are employed in compliance with applicable privacy, risk management, and continuous monitoring requirements.

CoreTrustSeal Board comment: Aspects pertaining to this characteristic are addressed in CoreTrustSeal Requirements R4. Confidentiality/Ethics, and R16. Security with a dependency on R5. Organizational infrastructure.

J. Common Format: Allows datasets and metadata to be downloaded, accessed, or exported from the repository in a standards-compliant, and preferably non-proprietary, format.

CoreTrustSeal Board comment: Aspects pertaining to this characteristic are addressed in CoreTrustSeal Requirement R14. Data reuse.

We suggest taking into account here that a format commonly used in a community may not always be “standards-compliant” and/or non-proprietary. We recommend expanding the statement to require that data, metadata, and documentation should be provided in formats that are consistent with the needs and practices of the community served.

K. Provenance: Maintains a detailed logfile of changes to datasets and metadata, including date and user, beginning with creation/upload of the dataset, to ensure data integrity.

CoreTrustSeal Board comment: Aspects pertaining to this characteristic are addressed in CoreTrustSeal Requirement R7. Data integrity and authenticity.

Important provenance information should also be made available to repository stakeholders. For this purpose, repositories also should employ version control of data, with naming conventions that communicate when a new version of the dataset has been released. We recommend in addition that pre-deposit provenance should be sought and available with the dataset, including information about the collection and processing of the dataset, prior to ingest.

“Logfile”: As this suggests a specific implementation of collecting provenance, it might be stated in a more abstract way (e.g., “methodology to record” or “audit trails”).

II. Additional Considerations for Repositories Storing Human Data (Even if De-Identified)

CoreTrustSeal Board comment: As “de-identification” and “anonymization” are not always considered synonymous², we suggest referring to both terms here.

A. *Fidelity to Consent:* Restricts dataset access to appropriate uses consistent with original consent (such as for use only within the context of research on a specific disease or condition)

CoreTrustSeal Board comment: This aligns with part of R4. Confidentiality/Ethics, which includes the guidance that “the repository should ensure that data collection or creation was carried out in accordance with legal and ethical criteria prevailing in the data producer’s geographical location or discipline”. The clarification of these rights falls under R2. Licenses.

B. *Restricted Use Compliant:* Enforces submitters’ data use restrictions, such as preventing reidentification or redistribution to unauthorized users.

CoreTrustSeal Board comment: For the CoreTrustSeal, the rights issues would be clarified through R2. Licenses. Evidence for other CoreTrustSeal Requirements is expected to align with the permissions, obligations, and prohibitions defined by those rights. Other protective measures would be applied through R16. Security. The repository’s responsibility to ensure that users understand and follow requirements for the use of restricted data also aligns with R4. Confidentiality/Ethics. The repository should also communicate to users of restricted data how best to ensure they are protected.

C. *Privacy:* Implements and provides documentation of security techniques appropriate for human subjects’ data to protect from inappropriate access.

CoreTrustSeal Board comment: The title here of “Privacy” (duplicative of I. *Privacy* above), has a number of overlaps with, and distinctions from “Confidentiality” in some geographic/legal areas. But, the content is primarily focused on information security.

CoreTrustSeal applicants holding human data would identify this under R4. Confidentiality/Ethics, document it through R2. Licenses, and demonstrate information security measures through R16. Security. Threats to confidentiality are not static, so as part of sustainability and preservation, a repository also should document how it maintains capabilities to ensure privacy as technology evolves.

² See, for example: Fullerton SM, Anderson NR, Guzauskas G, Freeman D, Fryer-Edwards K. Meeting the governance challenges of next-generation biorepository research. *Sci Transl Med.* 2010 Jan 20;2(15):15cm3. doi: 10.1126/scitranslmed.3000361. PMID: 20371468; PMCID: PMC3038212.

D. *Plan for Breach*: Has security measures that include a data breach response plan.

CoreTrustSeal Board comment: The need to plan and ideally conduct periodic tests for breach scenarios is valuable for all data collections, not only with those containing human subject data. This also applies to items E to H below, which are valuable measures to have in place for all digital assets. To restrict this recommendation to 'human' data might devalue the investment repositories make in these matters for all of their data. It is also important to note that non-human data, such as ecologically or culturally sensitive geographic data, is at risk without these measures.

E. *Download Control*: Controls and audits access to and download of datasets.

CoreTrustSeal Board comment: Provision of Access as a function is stated in CoreTrustSeal TDR Requirement R1. Mission. Control is implied through the application of R2. Licenses, and technical measures for Authentication and Authorization are mentioned in R16. Security. CoreTrustSeal would expect more rigorous access control for personal data, but appropriate technical and organizational measures to ensure that data can only be accessed and used in accordance with the stated license would have to be in place for all data.

F. *Clear Use Guidance*: Provides accompanying documentation describing restrictions on dataset access and use.

CoreTrustSeal Board comment: Conditions would be included under CoreTrustSeal Requirement R2. Licenses and communicated to users at the point of reuse. The license and any accompanying documentation should describe the conditions of use for any data, regardless of whether the data contain personally identifiable information (PII). But, it is especially critical for data that contain PII.

G. *Retention Guidelines*: Provides documentation on its guidelines for data retention.

CoreTrustSeal Board comment: It is not clear whether this applies to a general retention period (e.g., minimum number of years) or rules for re-appraisal of collections over time to make disposition/retention decisions. This would apply to all types of data in a collection, though for personal data there may be additional criteria to define the circumstances under which a dataset, or data related to one or more individuals, might be withdrawn; for example, in response to a request from a data subject.

H. *Violations*: Has plans for addressing violations of terms-of-use by users and data mismanagement by the repository.

CoreTrustSeal Board comment: The guidance for CoreTrustSeal Requirement R2. Licenses includes a request for "Documentation on measures in the case of noncompliance

with conditions of access and use”, while R4. Confidentiality/Ethics asks whether there are “measures in place if conditions are not complied with?”

I. *Request Review*: Has an established data access review or oversight group responsible for reviewing data use requests.

CoreTrustSeal Board comment: This is not explicitly requested by the CoreTrustSeal Requirements, but would usually form part of the license and rights negotiation at the point of deposit. The Requirements could usefully add a specific question about this process for applicants curating personal (or otherwise sensitive) data.